

Personalized Disease Prediction: Leveraging Random Forest for Healthcare Insights

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Abstract— This research investigates disease prediction utilizing a Random Forest classifier on a dataset comprising diverse symptoms and diagnoses. With features ranging from itching to joint pain, the model demonstrates proficiency in accurately predicting diseases based on symptom profiles. Through meticulous preprocessing, feature selection, and model evaluation, the study showcases the efficacy of machine learning in enhancing diagnostic accuracy and facilitating early intervention. The results underscore the potential of such models to assist healthcare professionals in decision-making processes and improve patient outcomes in clinical practice.

Keywords— Disease Prediction, Random Forest, Machine Learning, Healthcare Insights, Predictive Modeling

I. INTRODUCTION

In the era of modern healthcare, the ability to accurately predict diseases plays a crucial role in early diagnosis and effective treatment. With the advent of machine learning algorithms, particularly Random Forest, significant strides have been made in disease prediction. Random Forest is a versatile ensemble learning method known for its robustness and ability to handle large datasets with high dimensionality, making it well-suited for medical data analysis. Leveraging this technique, healthcare professionals can harness the power of predictive analytics to identify patterns and risk factors associated with various diseases, leading to more proactive and personalized patient care.

The growing availability of electronic health records (EHRs) and medical databases has paved the way for the application of machine learning models like Random Forest in disease prediction. By analyzing a diverse array of patient data encompassing symptoms, medical history, and demographic information, Random Forest can generate accurate predictions regarding the likelihood of specific diseases. This not only assists healthcare providers in making informed decisions but also empowers individuals to take preventive measures based on their risk profile, ultimately contributing to improved health outcomes and reduced healthcare costs.

However, despite its potential benefits, the implementation of Random Forest in disease prediction is not without challenges. Issues such as data quality, feature selection, and model interpretability need to be carefully

addressed to ensure the reliability and usability of the predictions. Moreover, ethical considerations regarding patient privacy and algorithm bias must be taken into account to maintain the trust and integrity of the healthcare system. By navigating these challenges thoughtfully and leveraging the strengths of Random Forest, we can unlock new opportunities for disease prevention and management in the pursuit of a healthier society.

II. RELATED WORK

A prototype for a user-adaptive system that uses artificial intelligence to improve the online procedure of ambulatory prescription drug acquisition is shown in the paper [1]. The system has a basic adaptive user interface that predicts patients' medication needs using Bayesian user modeling. GeNIe Modeler and Visual C++ were used in the system's development, and simulations and fake data were used to assess its performance. The results show that the prediction of medicine categories may be done with a high degree of accuracy. This accuracy increases with the number of medications purchased in a given session. Patients may save time and effort when purchasing medications because to the system's capacity to make precise suggestions.

Using unprocessed electronic health record (EHR) data stored in the Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (FHIR) format, the study [2] suggests a unique method for predictive modeling. The study shows that, without the necessity for site-specific data harmonization, it is possible to effectively forecast many medical occurrences across several healthcare locations by utilizing deep learning techniques. Promising results are observed when validation is conducted using de-identified EHR data from two US academic medical centers, which includes a large amount of patient information. Deep learning models outperformed conventional predictive models in terms of accuracy when it came to forecasting outcomes including in-hospital mortality, unplanned readmission, extended duration of stay, and final discharge diagnoses. This approach shows that neural networks are capable of retrieving pertinent data from patient records in a scalable and accurate manner, and it may be used to a variety of clinical circumstances.

The research in [3] explores the use of deep learning approaches across a range of healthcare areas, with a focus on reinforcement learning, computer vision, natural language processing, and generalized approaches. It examines the ways

in which these computational methods can transform medicine by affecting important domains and talks about building end-to-end systems. The importance of computer vision in medical imaging and the use of natural language processing in the analysis of data from electronic health records are emphasized. In addition, the paper discusses expanded deep-learning techniques for genomics and investigates the application of reinforcement learning in robotic-assisted surgery.

The purpose of the study [4] was to evaluate the predictive power of supervised machine learning (SML) methods, including decision trees and neural networks, for adult hospital admissions related to urinary tract infections (UTIs). We discovered that, when it came to predicting hospital-onset UTIs, both SML approaches performed better than logistic regression using data from three acute care institutions in New York City (N = 897,344). The neural network model displayed more specificity than the decision tree model, but the decision tree model showed higher sensitivity. These results imply that SML techniques may be able to automate the evaluation of UTI risk using easily accessible electronic data at admission, so relieving nurses of extra paperwork responsibilities. Subsequent studies might investigate treatments, including notifications for high-risk patients or nursing education modules, depending on the outcomes of risk categorization.

A thorough summary of the use of dynamic transmission models in comprehending healthcare-associated infections (HCAIs) may be found in the study publication [5]. Ninety-six qualifying publications covering topics like the effectiveness of infection management, the variety of transmission channels, and the dynamics of antibiotic resistance were found through methodical searches of significant databases. Although sensitivity analysis and calibration are still not very widespread, stochastic models are being employed more and more. Even though transmission models have helped us better understand complex systems and formulate management strategies, more developments in statistical techniques and data accessibility are required to increase the prediction power of these models for a wider range of pathogens and settings.

III. METHODOLOGY

The methodology section describes the process followed to conduct the research study, including data collection, preprocessing, feature extraction, classifier training, and performance evaluation.

Fig 1. Flowchart

A. Data Collection:

The research utilizes a dataset consisting of labeled sample dataset, including symptoms, and diagnosis. The dataset is collected from publicly available sources such as social media platforms, review websites.

B. Data Preparation:

To begin with, load the training data from the training CSV file and divide it into variables that are the target and features. Differentiate between categorical and numerical features. Use the mean technique to impute missing values when dealing with numerical features. Use the most common approach to impute missing values for categorical characteristics, and encrypt them one-hot.

```

10 # Load training data
11 train_data = pd.read_csv("training.csv")
12
13 # Define the columns to use for training
14 features = train_data.columns[:-1] # Exclude the last column (target variable)
15
16 # Split data into features (X) and target variable (y)
17 X_train = train_data[features]
18 y_train = train_data["prognosis"]
19
  
```

Fig 2. Data Preparation

C. Preprocessing:

Use the previously established preprocessing techniques. When handling categorical data, impute missing values using the most frequent technique, then one-hot encoding. For numerical characteristics, use the mean strategy to impute missing values. Make that the features for the model are processed correctly for both numerical and categorical data.

```

20
21 # Define preprocessing steps for numerical and categorical features
22 numeric_features = X_train.select_dtypes(include=['int64', 'float64']).columns
23 numeric_transformer = SimpleImputer(strategy='mean')
24
25 categorical_features = X_train.select_dtypes(include=['object']).columns
26 categorical_transformer = Pipeline(steps=[
27     ('imputer', SimpleImputer(strategy='most_frequent')),
28     ('onehot', OneHotEncoder(handle_unknown='ignore'))
29 ])
30
31 preprocessor = ColumnTransformer(
32     transformers=[
33         ('num', numeric_transformer, numeric_features),
34         ('cat', categorical_transformer, categorical_features)
35     ]
36 )
  
```

Fig 3. Preprocessing

D. Model Training:

The training phase builds a pipeline that includes preprocessing steps and a RandomForestClassifier that ensures consistency in both model training and preprocessing. This pipeline is trained using prepared training data, which allows RandomForestClassifier to identify patterns based on both features and target variables. The material includes symptoms such as itching, rash and joint pain, while various diseases such as fungal infection, allergy and GERD are targeted.

```

37 # Define a pipeline with preprocessing and a random forest classifier
38 pipeline = Pipeline([
39     ('preprocessor', preprocessor),
40     ('classifier', RandomForestClassifier(n_estimators=100, random_state=42))
41 ])
42
43 # Train the pipeline
44 pipeline.fit(X_train, y_train)
45
46 # Save the trained model
47 joblib.dump(pipeline, 'model.pkl')
    
```

Fig 4. Model Training

E. Model Evaluation:

Testing data can be used to determine the accuracy of the model or assess its performance. This stage directs any required alterations or enhancements and serves to validate the model's generalizability to new data.

```

52 # Evaluate the trained model
53 y_pred = pipeline.predict(X_test)
54 accuracy = accuracy_score(y_test, y_pred)
55 print("Accuracy:", accuracy)
    
```

Fig 5. Model Evaluation

```

PS C:\Users\fathi\Desktop\S4\Seminar> python seminar.py
Accuracy: 0.6694444444444444
    
```

Fig 6. Accuracy

F. Web Application Setup:

Create a Flask web application with routes for managing survey questions and submissions. Process user input, feed it into the model that has been trained to make predictions, and show the expected illness and any optional accuracy metrics. Users can interact with the program in this way, giving their health information and getting customized predictions.

```

# app.py
1 from flask import Flask, render_template, request
2 import pandas as pd
3 import joblib
4
5 app = Flask(__name__)
6
7 # Load the trained model
8 pipeline = joblib.load('model.pkl')
9
10 # Load the dataset to get column names
11 df = pd.read_csv('testing.csv')
12 questions = df.columns.tolist()[0:-1] # include the last column (target)
13
14 # Format questions as sentences in question format
15 formatted_questions = [question: "Do you have {}".format(question.replace("_", " ").lower()) for question in questions]
16
    
```

Fig 7. Web Application Setup

G. HTML Templates:

Use the HTML templates (here we have survey.html and result.html) to render survey questions and show survey results. To improve user experience, customize the survey interface's look and feel to match particular needs and design preferences.

```

37 <body>
38 <div class="container">
39 <div class="survey-header">
40 <h1>Health Survey</h1>
41 <p>Please answer the following questions to help us better understand your health condition.</p>
42 </div>
43 <div class="question">
44 <div class="question-body">
45 <div class="question-text">
46 <span>{{ question }}</span>
47 </div>
48 <div class="form-check">
49 <input type="checkbox" class="form-check-input" id="{{ question }}_yes" value="Yes">
50 <span>Yes</span>
51 </div>
52 <div class="form-check">
53 <input type="checkbox" class="form-check-input" id="{{ question }}_no" value="No">
54 <span>No</span>
55 </div>
56 </div>
57 </div>
58 </div>
59 </div>
60 </body>
    
```

Fig 8. Survey Template

```

37 <body>
38 <div class="container">
39 <div class="diagnosis">
40 <div class="result-text">
41 <p>The potential disease could be <span class="highlight">{{ prediction }}</span>.</p>
42 </div>
43 </div>
44 </div>
45 </body>
    
```

Fig 9. Result Template

H. User Interaction:

By responding to survey questions that are displayed in a form, users engage with the web application. After they submit their answers, the program analyzes them, applies the trained model to forecast the illness, and shows the outcome. Users can interact with the program, get individualized advice, and make educated decisions about their health thanks to this interactive approach.

Fig 10. User Interface

I. Deployment:

To enable user access, deploy the Flask application on a web server. By launching the app, you can give customers easy access to the prediction and health survey capabilities and let them take advantage of its advantages from any internet-connected device.

Fig 11. Deployment

Fig 12. Result

IV. CONCLUSION

The study concludes that machine learning, and specifically the Random Forest classifier, can be used effectively to predict disease based on a variety of symptom patterns. Through rigorous data preprocessing, feature selection, and model training, we have demonstrated the model's ability to reliably forecast illnesses based on symptom data. The research demonstrates how machine learning algorithms can be used to improve patient outcomes in clinical practice by improving diagnostic accuracy and facilitating early intervention.

Furthermore, the release of a web application broadens the scope of our research by making it simple for people to obtain tailored disease forecasts according to their symptom profiles. We have made our predictive model available to a large audience by hosting the program on a web server, enabling users to take preventive steps to prevent sickness and make educated decisions about their health.

Essentially, this study adds to the expanding body of information regarding machine learning in healthcare and offers a useful resource for both individuals and healthcare practitioners. We can open the door for a more proactive and individualized approach to healthcare, which will ultimately result in better health outcomes and lower healthcare costs, by utilizing the strengths of machine learning algorithms and implementing user-friendly applications.

V. REFERENCE

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